

Voice Related Quality Of Life and Psychological Well-Being Among Transgenders

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: November 11, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: June 16, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Transgender, Quality Of Life, Voice, Psychological Well Being</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6653723</p>	<p>Background: In recent years, there has been an increase in interest in the subject of voice difficulties and treatment among transgender people, a study about voice related quality of life among transgender is needed.</p> <p>Objective: To find out the voice-related quality of life and psychological well-being of transgender.</p> <p>Methodology: Observational Cross-Sectional Study with purposive sampling technique. Total number of participants were N=377 who were transgender approached at Fountain House Lahore. Two standardized questionnaires; Voice related quality of life (V-RQOL) and Psychological Wellbeing Scale were given to the participants. Data was presented through frequency and percentages.</p> <p>Results: Result shows 34.8% (132) participants were having lowest psychological well-being, while 38.5 % (146) participants were having moderate and 26.6 % (101) were having highest psychological well-being. 19.5 % (74) participants were having excellent voice related quality of life and had no trouble in their voice related quality of life. 22.4% (85) were having very good voice quality while 26.4% (100) were having fair or 13.2% (50) were having poor voice quality of life.</p> <p>Conclusion: Majority of transgender have average score on psychological wellbeing scale while majority of transgender have fair voice related quality of life.</p>

Introduction

Individuals communicate their ideas and feelings via their voices, which are the most important weapon in their arsenal of communication tools. People's ability to communicate is becoming more important as society advances and medical technology advances at an exponential rate (Yu et al., 2019). People's capacity to communicate, daily living routines, emotional and economic functioning, and, ultimately, fundamental quality of life may suffer because of vocal issues. The significance of the voice cannot be stressed enough for professional voice users, such as teachers, singers, and attorneys. Voice-related disorders, on the other hand, can have a big negative impact on a person's quality of life and ability to work in their jobs (Sheyona & Devadas, 2022).

Objective speech assessment tools, like imaging technology and acoustic aspects, may not be able to consider an individual's everyday experiences and how they interact with the world around them. Transgender people, also known as "transsexuals," are individuals whose gender identity differs from the sex into which they were born due to physical and sexual characteristics (Maughan et al., 2022). Numerous studies have shown that, as compared to the general population, transgender women and men experience greater rates of psychological discomfort in general, as well as depressive symptoms, poor self-esteem, and suicide (Contreras-Ruston et al., 2021).

Because of the convergence and confluence of oppressions known as transmisogyny, those who identify as transgender are more likely than others to experience mental health difficulties. According to the study, discrimination, depressive symptoms, low self-esteem, and suicide thoughts have all been linked to transgender women in a variety of demographic groups (Coburn et al., 2022).

There are mental health disparities for transgender youngsters, as seen by the higher levels of despair and anxiety they experienced compared to their cisgender peers. This study investigated the relationship between social support and the overall well-being and resilience of transgender children by using a number of research methods (Menezes et al., 2022). Fewer people in the previous year reported having a mental health problem when they had more family support. Results show there is no evident influence of friendship or significant other support on one's ability to live as one's declared gender (Millet et al., 2016).

Danielle and her coworkers conducted a sectional study on this problem. Gender identity was evaluated in the recordings of transgender and cisgender women using acoustic features, emotional prosody and self-perception. For example, transgender women's first three vowel formants and emotional prosody are distinct from those of

cisgender women (which includes length and melodic contour)(Aronu et al., 2021). For example, the cisgender population's noise intensity and voice level was consistently higher. Transgender women's voices were overwhelmingly mistaken for those of males by the great majority of those who heard them.

It is estimated that in the United States, Turner syndrome affects one in every 2,500 females (TS)(Chen, 2022).A variety of psychiatric problems, as well as poor general health and well-being, have been documented by women with TS in previous studies (QoL). The statistics, on the other hand, are mostly directed at young girls, with adult women receiving small, inconsistent, and sometimes insufficient sample sizes (Busa et al., 2018). In light of the particular challenges that adult women with TS confront, further study is needed to address their specific needs. More than 301 women aged 16 to 73 years old with TS were studied and compared for their quality of life, including depression, anxiety, self-esteem and attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD)(Franik et al., 2019).

To date, no research has been conducted to assess the psychological well-being of the transgender community with respect to the quality of life related to their voice production. Similarly, there is a scarcity of research on the issue of voice on its own.It is the most important demand of the world we live in that this group be encouraged to engage in research in order to evaluate their issues, which we are presently unaware of. As a consequence of the results, this research will result in better lives for underprivileged people, as well as a more welcoming and accepting society.

Methodology

It was an Observational Cross-Sectional Study with purposive sampling technique.Total number of participants was n=379 who were transgender approached at fountain House Lahore. Sample size was calculated by using the formula of prevalence. Hence the calculated was 377. Sample was calculated on the basis of prevalence of quality of life among transgenders 17.Two standardized questionnaires; Voice related quality of life (V-RQOL) and Psychological Wellbeing Scale were given to the participants. Inclusion criteria was based on following points.Both klenifilter male trans gender and turner female transgender will be included.Aged 18 to 50 years above was included. Trans from Lahore was included. Transgenders below 18 years were not included. Those having psychical and mental issues, Genomic pattern is excluded. Individual who pretended to be transgender was excluded.Data was presented through frequency and percentages. Their genomic pattern was excluded out of research.

Results

Table 1: Demographic information of participants (N=377)

Education	Frequency	Percent			
Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Age	379	13.00	90.00	50.4274	12.11199
Illiterate				209	55.1
Primary				87	23.0
Middle				39	10.3
Matric				38	10.0
Intermediate				1	.3
Others				1	.3
Marital Status					
Single				364	96.0
Married				13	3.4
Other				2	.5
Profession					
Beggar				355	93.7
Music and Art				4	1.1
Not Mentioned				12	3.2

Business/Job	8	2.1
Area of Residency		
Rural	8	2.1
Urban	371	97.9
Living Status		
Living with Biological Parents	3	.8
Living without Biological Parents	376	99.2

Table 2 describes that 55.1% (209) participants were illiterate, 23.0% (87) were primary, 10.3% (39) were middle, 10.0(38) were metric, while intermediate are .3 %(1), and others are .3(1).while(,96.0) (364) participants were single , 3.4% (13) were single. 93.7 %(355) were belong from begging profession, 1.1 %(4) belong from music and arts. 3.2(12) were not mentioned their profession 2.1 %(8) were doing business and jobs. 2.1 %(8) were belong from rural area, 97.3% (371) were belong from urban area. .8% were living with their biological parents, 99.2 %(376) were living without their biological parents.

Table 2: Psychological Well-being among transgender

Level of Psychological well-being	Frequency	Percent
Lowest Psychological wellbeing	132	34.8
Moderate	146	38.5
Highest Psychological wellbeing	101	26.6

Table 2 describes the psychological well-being among transgender. In this table result shows that 34.8% (n=132) participants were having lowest psychological well-being, while 38.5% (n=146) participants were having moderate and 26.6 % (n=101) were having highest psychological well-being. This identifies that their psychological well being is not of highest quality in majority, but of moderate level.

Table 3: Voice related quality of Life

VQRL	Frequency	Percent
Excellent	74	19.5
very good	85	22.4
Good	70	18.5
Fair	100	26.4
Poor	50	13.2

Table 3 describes the voice related quality of life of transgender. Result shows that 19.5 % (n=74) participants were having excellent voice related quality of life and had no trouble in their voice related quality of life. 22.4% (n=85) were having very good voice quality while 26.4% (n=100) were having fair and 13.2% (n=50) were having poor voice related quality of life.

By comparing both the results obtained from the data of both the performas, no association is established between voice related quality of life and its effect on psychological well being of transgender.

Discussion

Speech and language impairment was common in all 50 guys with Klinefelter syndrome (KS). The research sample was still tiny, thus the specific communication strengths and weaknesses of the group were yet unclear. No research has been done to prove that children's ability to communicate is stable across a wide range of ages, from infancy to adolescence. In order to get a better knowledge of children and adolescents with KS, this research sought to categorize and identify them(Herlihy et al., 2011). At one year and one month old, the youngest participant in the research was the youngest participant in the study. Additionally, this research focused on the oromotor system, which includes the ability to talk and read as well as the ability to comprehend language(Gunjawate, B. Kumar, Ravi and Kunnath, 2020). Ninety-two percent of patients (24/26) experienced communication issues, with the most common being difficulties with interpersonal and pragmatic language (15/18; 83%), language memory (12/15; 80%), and literacy (13/17; 76%)(Robinson, 2022). Receptive and expressive language deficits were found in 70 percent of the participants in this study, with moderate to severe language difficulties found in 16 of the 23 participants (70 percent). Almost all of the subjects (21 out of 21; 100 percent) had some kind of oromotor or speech problem throughout their whole life span(Nobili, Glazebrook and Arcelus, 2018).The results are not in accordance with our research where the voice related quality of life was good overall.

Only a small percentage of the world's population has been studied for their disparities in mental health (Priest, 2019). As part of this research, transgender people in New Zealand and Aotearoa/New Zealand are compared to the general population's mental health from infancy to old age. In 2018, a survey of 1178 people was conducted on mental health (Foster Skewis et al., 2021). The Kessler Psychological Distress Scale (K10) and diagnoses of depression and anxiety disorders were used to assess participants' mental health (Lindley et al., 2022). There were a lot of elements in this survey that were comparable. The mental health of transgender individuals, particularly young transgender people, is severely lacking. Since this community's mental health and well-being is at stake, it is imperative that regulations at institutions are inclusive and protect them from stress resulting from gender minorities. Same results were established in our research showing poor psychological well being of transgender (Buckley et al., 2020).

Anxiety disorders are the most common mental illness in the general population. Over the course of a year, anxiety problems affect around 18% of Americans and 13.6% of Europeans respectively (lifetime prevalence (Warren et al., 2016). Transgender persons are more likely to suffer from anxiety disorders and anxiety-related symptoms than the general population, according to several studies. Few studies have revealed the specific anxiety problems that transgender people suffer from (particularly in terms of gender predominance). (Treharne et al., 2022) Anxiety disorders and their symptoms are the focus of this study, which collects and evaluates data from studies that have been made available to the general public (Catalpa et al., 2019). Eight longitudinal studies with a total of eight individuals and 25 cross-sectional studies with a total of 17 people have been uncovered in the study (Treharne et al., 2022)." The transgender community, compared to the overall population, shows much more anxiety symptoms, according to cross-sectional studies. Anxiety affects between 17 and 68 percent of the population on a daily basis, according to extensive research (Glynn et al., 2016). There was a high prevalence of specific phobias, such as social phobia and panic disorder, followed by generalized anxiety disorders among the research participants (Nobili et al., 2018).

Conclusion

With respect to the psychological well being of transgender, most of them (n=146) had it at moderate level followed by the number (n=132) that had lowest psychological well being. Over all voice related quality of life was found good.

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